

GINNIGER

From Barriers to Action

Policy Insights for Advancing Urban
Regeneration in **Switzerland**

Co-funded by the
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About GINNGER

The GINNGER project aims to create new, inclusive and participatory processes for **neighbourhood regeneration**. A **methodology** to support collaborative **decision-making** is at the project's core. GINNGER is also designing and implementing regeneration plans across six pilot sites in Europe. Four key areas of regeneration are involved: energy efficiency, renovation of buildings and urban spaces, efficient use of resources and sustainable mobility.

**GINNGER | Co-designing
neighbourhood regeneration**

The Swiss policy context

In Switzerland, the regulatory framework already strongly supports **local energy initiatives**. The Federal Energy Act promotes **self-consumption, energy efficiency** and **renewable generation**, while the Electricity Supply Act enables **decentralised production** while ensuring grid stability. In Ticino, cantonal laws further encourage PV deployment, building efficiency and **renewable integration**. Additional improvements could include **clearer rules** for Local Energy Communities (CLE), peer-to-peer energy exchange, flexibility markets, and better collection of mobility and vehicle-flow data to support local planning and policy evaluation.

Barriers, Opportunities and Recommendations

	Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variation in participatory planning requirements across municipalities. • Existing rules about energy consumption in buildings. Weak integration of circular construction principles in local policies. • Requirements for renewable energy integration in new buildings.
	Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laws promote self-consumption and energy efficiency measures and active consumer participation. Strong national support for large-scale renovation funding. • Advanced cantonal energy standards support deep renovation. • Ongoing national debate on legislative updates for energy sharing. • Existing laws facilitate the implementation of local energy communities and collective self-consumption schemes. • National and cantonal incentive schemes support the energy transition.
	Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on a clearer operational definition of the newest local community of energy (CLE). • Provide additional regulatory clarification for peer-to-peer energy exchange within energy communities, to enable transparent and scalable local markets. • Set out more explicit roles and responsibilities in flexibility markets. • Promote the collection and monitoring of data on mobility and vehicle flows to provide better input for local transport policies.

Conclusions and next steps

The recommendations presented are **based on GIUNGER's pilots of Massagno's experience**. They aim to support authorities and policymakers to facilitating and standardising neighbourhood renovation and collaborative decision-making at the national and local level. During the next months, the project partners will expand this analysis, identifying **best practices and potential areas for harmonisation** in all pilot sites and in all four key areas of regeneration (energy efficiency, renovation of buildings and urban spaces, efficient use of resources, and sustainable mobility).

Methodology

The analysis presented was based on data collected through the assessment of policy and regulatory drivers and barriers (conducted under GIUNGER's Task 2.4), and through questionnaires circulated among pilot partners.

Sources and further information

¹ [Piano energetico cantonale \(PEC\) - PEC \(TICH\) - Repubblica e Cantone Ticino](#)

² [Energy Strategy 2050](#)

³ [Legge cantonale sull'energia dell'8 febbraio 1994 \(Len\)](#)

⁴ [RUEN](#)

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